

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

THE SPECTRUM OF MASSES OF ELEMENTARY PARTICLES, RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MICRO- AND MACRO-SCALES, RELATIONSHIP AMONG COSMIC ENERGIES

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Abstract

Alternate hypothesis for the concepts of the matter structurization is set out. The mass values of some known as well as previously unknown particles have been theoretically obtained on a basis of new results conformities to natural law. This hypothesis provides the means of indegration of world of micropartiles with cosmological concepts as dark energy and dark matter.

Keywords: dark matter, dark energy, vacuum, spectrum of masses.

Introduction

Until very recently, it was agreed that the building of contemporary physics had already essentially been erected. The only some additions are to be made and the further advancement of physics is deadlock. However, a body of recent astronomical investigations has uncovered that the picture of the Universe has been something of a mystery or in more exact terms, is not satisfied earlier notions. These astronomical investigation results are, above all, accelerated expansion of negative pressure of vacuum or dark energy (“quintessence”). Besides, there is invisible dark matter surrounding galaxies. The constitution of this matter is unknown. The common baryon substance forming the stars is only small part of the Universe mass.

In addition, there is “something” in Solar system. This “something” retarded the motion of cosmic sondes “Pioneer”, launched at the 1970s and gave no way to escape the limits of Solar system.

Together these and many others facts cause us to take a fresh look at eternal questions: what is the matter and what is the space? What is manner in which the world of microparticles and macroscales are related to each other? What is the association between gravitation and other interactions? It is obvious that such relationship is to be. This article is concerned with abovementioned questions.

1. The elementary charge and the spectrum of masses of elementary particles or why the μ -meson is 207 times heavier than electron

The nature surrounding us is unified and laws controlling the world of microparticles are inextricably entwined with the laws of shaping and progression of matter macrostructures and the Universe as a whole. The gravitation as physical field and inertia are the base for the shaping of the all interactions of forces and charges of macro- and microworld.

The electron is fundamental and stable particle having elementary electrical charge. Think of a electron as a “system” containing the virtual Planck particle of spin h with dimension $r_{pl} = \left(\frac{Gh}{c^3}\right)^{1/2}$, and virtual particle m , radially “moving” in scale r in the rotating field of gravitation of the Planck particle.

Let us assume that the energy of electrical charge is

$$\frac{e^2}{r} = \frac{h^2}{mr^2} \cdot \frac{r_{pl}^2}{r^2} \quad (1)$$

This relation may be written as:

$$r = \frac{h^2}{me^2} \cdot \frac{r_{pl}^2}{r^2}$$

and now the relation is somewhat similar to the Bohr quantum conditions:

$$r_n = \frac{h^2 \cdot n^2}{m_e \cdot e^2}$$

Considering the value of r_{pl} , the r would be expressible as:

$$r = \frac{h}{c} \left(\frac{G}{me^2}\right)^{1/3} \quad (2)$$

Assigning to the masses of virtual particles m the quantum numbers $m_n = m_0 \cdot e^{-n^2}$, where m_0 is the mass of most heavy particle (subsequent to m_{pl}) and $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 12$, we derives

$$r_n = \frac{h}{c} \left(\frac{G}{m_0 \cdot e^{-n^2} \cdot e^2} \right)^{1/3}. \quad (3)$$

Table 1

n	1	2	3	4
$m_{obs}(m_e)$	1.4	3.8	20	207
$m_{vir}(m_e)$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{20}$	$1.3 \cdot 10^{19}$	$8.6 \cdot 10^{16}$	$7.8 \cdot 10^{13}$
$l_{vir}(cm)$	10^{-31}	10^{-30}	10^{-27}	10^{-24}
$2r_n(cm)$	$2 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-31}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-30}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-29}$
n	5	6	7	8
$m_{obs}(m_e)$	4160	162700	$1.2 \cdot 10^7$	$1.8 \cdot 10^9$
$m_{vir}(m_e)$	10^{10}	162700	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-7}$
$l_{vir}(cm)$	10^{-20}	10^{-16}	10^{-10}	10^{-4}
$2r_n(cm)$	$4 \cdot 10^{-28}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-26}$	$3 \cdot 10^{-24}$	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-22}$
n	9	10	11	12
$m_{obs}(m_e)$	$5.3 \cdot 10^{11}$	$3 \cdot 10^{14}$	$3.3 \cdot 10^{17}$	$7 \cdot 10^{20}$
$m_{vir}(m_e)$	$4.6 \cdot 10^{-15}$	$2.6 \cdot 10^{-23}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-32}$	$2 \cdot 10^{-42}$
$l_{vir}(cm)$	10^4	$10^{12} \div 10^{13}$	$10^{21} \div 10^{22}$	10^{31}
$2r_n(cm)$	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-19}$	10^{-16}	10^{-13}	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-10}$

It is suggested that the observed mass of particle is bound with this dimension by simple relation

$$m_{obs} = kr,$$

where k is constant.

Assume that the particle is electron at $n = 0$, $m_{vir} = m_0$. Its dimension is $r_0 \sim 10^{-31}$ cm (do not confuse with the classical electron radius). Inserting $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 12$ in Eq.3, we arrive the dimensionless relations or $\frac{m_{obsn}}{m_e}$, as

mentioned above. Arrange the arrived relations in tabulated form (Table 1, first line).

By this means the masses of observed particles increase up to

$$7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e \sim 3.5 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ GeV } (n=12).$$

When $n = 13$, mass of particles are greater than mass of Planck ($1.2 \cdot 10^{19}$ GeV).

On the assumption that this mass is m_0 in Eq. 3, we calculate the second line of Table. The dimension of virtual particle (wave length), compatible with its mass is in third line of Table. In fourth line of Table we calculate the “doubled” radius (3). When n is major the wave lengths of virtual particles are enormous. However, it should be remembered that in the “constitution” of observed particles these virtual particles are in the “bound” and not free state.

Once again, we call attention to the observed particles

$$\begin{array}{l|l} \frac{r_1}{r_0} = 1.4, & \text{at } n = 1, \\ \frac{r_2}{r_0} = 3.8, & \text{at } n = 2, \\ \frac{r_3}{r_0} = 20, & \text{at } n = 3, \\ \hline \frac{r_4}{r_0} = 207, & \text{at } n = 4, \\ \frac{r_5}{r_0} = 4160, & \text{at } n = 5, \\ \frac{r_6}{r_0} = 162700, & \text{at } n = 6. \end{array}$$

When $n = 4, 5, 6$ these relations somewhat resemble, with known error, masses of μ^- meson, τ^- meson and w^- boson expressed in terms of the masses of electron.

The mass of actual τ^- lepton is less than mass of (4160) state by value of mass (or binding energy which is equal to this mass) of two virtual π^- mesons which are the disintegration product of τ^- lepton in parallel with ν_τ . Consequently, the part of energy of this state is used for the binding energy of two π^- mesons.

Hadrons or strong interaction particles may be expressed as derivatives of μ , τ and w states:

$$\begin{matrix} \mu\text{-hadron} & \tau\text{-hadron} & w\text{-hadron} \\ \begin{pmatrix} \pi, p, n \\ u, d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} K \\ S \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} J/\Psi \\ d \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \gamma \\ S \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} t\text{-quarks} \\ S \end{pmatrix} \end{matrix}$$

where $d(1.4)$, $u(3.8)$, $S(1.4 \times 3.8)$ are levels.

Table 2

n	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	Note
	e	d	u	c	μ	τ	w	
e^-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	
μ^-	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	
τ^-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	
π^-	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	$\uparrow\downarrow S$
	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	
p^+	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	d
	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	$u \uparrow\downarrow\uparrow S$
	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	u
n^0	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	d
	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	$d \uparrow\downarrow\uparrow S$
	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	u
K^-	+	+	+	-	+	-	-	$\uparrow\downarrow S$
	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	
J/Ψ	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	$c\bar{c}$
	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	
γ	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	$b\bar{b}$
	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	
W^-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	$\uparrow\uparrow S$
	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	
Z^0	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	$\uparrow\uparrow S$
	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	
$t\bar{t}$	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	$t\bar{t}$
	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	

The masses of γ -meson and J/Ψ -meson are in the ratio as masses of K and π -mesons.

$$\frac{m_\gamma}{m_{J/\Psi}} = \frac{11020 \text{ MeV}}{3100 \text{ MeV}} \approx \frac{m_K}{m_\pi} \cong 3.5.$$

Likewise the masses of associated b and c -quarks are in the ratio: $\frac{4.6 \text{ GeV}}{1.3 \text{ GeV}} \cong 3.5$.

In such a manner, it has been proposed that J/Ψ particle (or $c\bar{c}$) is τ state of π -meson and γ particle (or $b\bar{b}$) is τ state of K - meson. D and B -mesons are the combinations of corresponding c and b quarks with quarks of μ -state.

The Table 1 is shown that mass of virtual particle is equal to mass of observed particle at $n = 6$. The mass of virtual particle at $n = 0$ is equal to mass of observed particle at $n = 12$ ($7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e$). These particles ($n = 6, n = 12$) are W and X – bosons respectively. t -quark is W^- state of K^- meson. W^- state of π^- meson and state with $n = 3$ are not realized as particles.

It should be noted that the ratio of the masses of existing hadrons to the masses of quarks is identical order as the ratio of masses of μ , τ and w states

$$\frac{m_\gamma}{m_k} \sim \frac{m_{J/\Psi}}{m_\pi} \sim \frac{m_\tau}{m_\mu} \sim 20; \frac{m_t}{m_b} \sim \frac{m_W}{m_\tau} \sim 40.$$

According to quantum states the elementary particles may be shown in tabulated form (see Table 2). It is evident from the Table that the particle is the combination of two or more states (with the exception of electron). The particles with one or two quantum levels are interacting only rarely.

The particles with three levels and up are hadrons.

The birth of massive lepton with $n = 7$ and mass about 6 Tev is likely with on further increasing the energy of colliders.

Once again, we call attention to the Table 1. As supposed above, a electron is structure containing the virtual particle of mass m_0 (heaviest after of m_{pl} , $n = 12$, $m = 7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e$), «moving» in radius $r_0 \sim 10^{-31}$ cm. The particle m_0 itself is made up by the «cloud» from lightest particle of mass $2 \cdot 10^{-42} m_e$, «moving» in radius r_{12} .

Now work out the $2r_{12}$ or Compton length for the electron:

$$2r_{12} = \frac{2h}{c} \left(\frac{G}{m_0 \cdot e^{-144} \cdot e^2} \right)^{1/3} \quad (n = 12), \quad (4)$$

where $m_0 = m_e \frac{r_{12}}{r_0} = m_e \cdot e^{\frac{144}{3}} \cong 7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e$.

Alternatively, Compton length for the electron is equal to

$$\lambda_e = \frac{h}{m_e c} = 2r_{12}$$

Equating this value to Eq. 4, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} m_e^3 &= \frac{m_e \cdot e^{\frac{144}{3}} \cdot e^{-144} \cdot e^2}{8G} \Rightarrow \\ \Rightarrow m_e &= \frac{e \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{1}{3} \cdot 144\right)}{\sqrt{8G}} = m_0 \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{144}{3}\right), \end{aligned}$$

where $m_0 = \frac{e}{\sqrt{8G}}$ is magnetic monopole (e is electron charge, G is gravity constant).

As a result we obtain:

$$2r_{12} = \frac{h}{m_e c} = \frac{h}{c} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{8G}}{e} \cdot \exp\left(\frac{144}{3}\right) \cong 2.4 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ cm}$$

Consequently, $2r_{12} \cong 2.4 \cdot 10^{-10}$ cm at $n = 12$, this value is correlated with Compton length for the electron.

We obtain $2r_{11} \cong 1.2 \cdot 10^{-13}$ cm at $n = 11$, this value is correlated with characteristic of the range of strong interaction.

The heavy particles mass whereby the “Great” union, as it is called, occurs and, which controls the life time of proton is $3.3 \cdot 10^{17} m_e$ or $10^{14} \div 10^{15}$ GeV.

$2r_{10} \cong 10^{-16}$ cm at $n = 10$ we obtain the characteristic of the range of slight interaction.

Consequently, the mass $\frac{r_{12}}{r_0}$ of heaviest particle m_0 or χ - particle is $7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e$. This mass is above the mass

of “Great” union. The mass or lightest particle is $2 \cdot 10^{-42} m_e$. Hence, the “dynamic range” of mass spectrum is $3.5 \cdot 10^{62} = e^{144}$. We designate this “dynamic range” as constant α or **constant of inflation**. We shall cover this constant later.

For the time being, we point out that the Eq. (1), for macroscale (e.g. the Earth), will be occur as:

$$\frac{Q^2}{r} = m \cdot \frac{V_{es}^2}{c^2} \cdot \dot{r}^2 \cdot \frac{\omega^2 r}{g_0} \cdot \frac{g(r)}{g_0},$$

where, Q is induced charge, m – the body mass having radial component of velocity $\dot{r}$ in the field rotating with frequency ω in gravity field of massive body with potential $V_{es}^2 = \frac{GM}{r}$ - escape velocity squared, g_0 – the acceleration of gravity on surface of massive rotating body. When substituting

$$\omega = \frac{h}{mr^2}, \quad V_{es}^2 = \frac{m_{pl} G}{r}, \quad g_0 = \frac{m_{pl} G}{r^2}, \quad \frac{g(r)}{g_0} = \frac{r_{pl}^2}{r^2}, \quad Q = e, \quad \dot{r} = c$$

we obtain the Eq. (1). It seems likely that this mechanism is universal and produces the electromagnetic effects which arise at radial motion of bodies in the rotating gravity field of massive body.

In the integrated form, this is expressible as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\varphi}{c^2} \cdot \int_V [\vec{r} \vec{v}] \rho dV = \oint_S [\vec{E} \vec{H}] dS \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\varphi}{c^2} \cdot \frac{\partial L}{\partial t} = W_{em},$$

where $\varphi = \frac{GM}{r}$ is potential, L - torque, W – electromagnetic energy.

By this is meant that the variation in the torque, inside the surface S , implies a flow of electromagnetic energy through this surface.

2. On the association of macroscales and microscales and feasible scenario of the progress of the Universe

1. If we denote the abovementioned value $e^{144} \cong 3.5 \cdot 10^{62}$ by α , then the association between the radius of the Universe and the Planck radius is:

$$\alpha \cdot l_{\text{pl}} = R_U \cong 3 \cdot 10^{29} \text{ cm},$$

and between the mass of the Universe and Planck mass is

$$\alpha \cdot m_{\text{pl}} = M_U \cong 10^{57} \text{ g}.$$

2. If the maximum density of substance is $\frac{m_{\text{pl}}}{l_{\text{pl}}^3}$ (that is the Planck mass per the quantum of space) and if we

suppose that the minimum density of substance is $\frac{m_{\text{pl}}}{(\alpha \cdot l_{\text{pl}})^3}$, that, on other hand, is the mass quantum per the

all “range” of space, we obtain:

$$\rho_{\text{min}} \cong \frac{10^{-5} \text{ g}}{10^{88} \text{ cm}^3} \cong 10^{-93} \text{ g/cm}^3; \quad R_U^3 = 10^{88} \text{ cm}^3,$$

in which case the Universe mass is:

$$\frac{\alpha \cdot m_{\text{pl}}}{\alpha \cdot R_U^3} = \frac{M_U}{\alpha \cdot R_U^3} = \rho_{\text{min}}; \quad \alpha \cdot R_U^3 = R_{\text{cr}}^3$$

and critical radius is

$$R_{\text{cr}} = \alpha^{1/3} \cdot R_U \cong 10^{50} \text{ cm} = \alpha^{4/3} \cdot l_{\text{pl}}$$

This value is in close agreement with the life time of proton multiplied by the velocity of light:

$$R_{\text{cr}} = c \tau_p \cong 10^{50} \text{ cm}, \quad \tau_p = 10^{33} \text{ years} \sim 10^{40} \text{ s}$$

3. At the instant of the generation (formation) of the Universe, the period of exponential expansion (inflation) – radius and mass (as one of dimensions) of six-dimensional structure (Planck element) increased by $\alpha = e^{144}$ раз. That is

$$R_U = \frac{l_{\text{pl}}}{2} \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{62} \approx 2.5 \cdot 10^{29} \text{ cm}, \quad \left(l_{\text{pl}} = \sqrt{\frac{G\hbar}{c^3}} \cong 1.5 \cdot 10^{33} \text{ cm} \right).$$

$$M_U = 2 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot 3.5 \cdot 10^{62} \approx 7 \cdot 10^{57} \text{ g}, \quad \left(M_{\text{pl}} = \sqrt{\frac{c\hbar}{G}} \cong 2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ g} \right).$$

At the same time, the sixdimensional sphere of Planck decays into χ - particles ($n=12$) with mass

$$m_{\chi} = \frac{e}{\sqrt{8G}} \approx 7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e = 3.5 \cdot 10^{17} \text{ GeV}, \text{ that is that competing on equal terms, six dimensions}$$

decay in to substance and space-time.

The ratio between Planck mass and χ - particle mass is

$$\frac{m_{\text{pl}}}{m_{\chi}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{c\hbar}{G}}}{\frac{e}{\sqrt{8G}}} \cong 33.1 = \sqrt{\frac{8}{\alpha_{\text{fs}}}}$$

where $\alpha_{\text{fs}} = \frac{e^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{1}{137}$ is constant of fine structure (not to be confused with inflation constant α).

The area of six dimensional sphere in seven dimensional space is

$$S_6 = \frac{16}{15} \pi^3 R^6 \cong 33.07 R^6$$

that is that the Planck six dimensional sphere “involves” $\left(\frac{m_{pl}}{m_\chi}\right)^6$ χ - particles (since the mass is one of dimensions).

$$\left(\frac{m_{pl}}{m_\chi}\right)^6 = 1.3 \cdot 10^9 = \beta = \frac{n_\gamma}{n_B}$$

is the fundamental constant of cosmology which are responsible for the baryon asymmetry of the Universe (ratio between amount of photons of relict rays and baryons per unit of volume).

Alternatively, from the experimental data, constant β is worked out as:

$$\beta = \frac{n_\gamma}{n_B} = \frac{400}{3 \cdot 10^{-7}} \approx 1.3 \cdot 10^9$$

where n_B is density of baryons

$$n_B = \frac{N}{V} = \frac{4.4 \cdot 10^{81}}{1.5 \cdot 10^{88}} \cong 3 \cdot 10^{-7} \frac{1}{\text{cm}^3}$$

it is the present-day evolution from astronomical data.

$$V = (2.5 \cdot 10^{29} \text{ cm})^3 \cong 1.5 \cdot 10^{88} \text{ cm}^3$$

is the Universe volume.

$$N = \frac{7 \cdot 10^{57} \text{ g}}{1.6 \cdot 10^{-24} \text{ g}} = \frac{M_U}{m_p} \cong 4.4 \cdot 10^{81}$$

is amount of baryons (m_p – mass of proton). $n_\gamma \cong 400 \frac{1}{\text{cm}^3}$ is density of photons of relict radiation.

That is that the above calculated value is in close agreement with evaluation obtained by experimental methods.

4. Thus, at first stage of rising of matter, at $n = 12$ and $E \sim 10^{17}$ GeV within the first 10^{-6} s (before hadron era), the quark $\leftrightarrow$ lepton transformations take place. These transformations are followed by the rising of lightest particles in amount of:

$$N_{12} = \frac{T_{12}}{\tau_{12}} N \beta = \frac{10^{-6} \text{ s}}{1.7 \cdot 10^{-42} \text{ s}} \cdot 1.3 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 4.4 \cdot 10^{81} \cong 3 \cdot 10^{126}$$

where $\tau_{12} = \beta^{1/6} \cdot \tau_{pl} = 33.1 \cdot \tau_{pl} \cong 1.7 \cdot 10^{-42} \text{ s}$ is characteristic time of the rising of these particles.

With decreasing energy to $3.3 \cdot 10^{17} m_e \sim 10^{14}$ GeV (energy of integration of electro-weak and strong interactions $n = 11$ (see Table 1)), the rising-decay of baryons takes place. In the modern view, at ultra-high temperatures and densities the plausible characteristic time of the rising-decay of baryon in quark-baryon plasma is of the order of 10^{-28} – 10^{-29} sec. This process extends about 10^{-4} sec since the onset of explosion and up to 10^{13} K.

Each of the of rising-decay of baryon are followed by the rise of light particle

$$n = 11; m = 2 \cdot 10^{-32} m_e; r = 10^{21} \div 10^{22} \text{ cm (see Table. 1).$$

The total amount of these light particle is:

$$N_{11} = N \beta \frac{10^{-4} \text{ s}}{\tau} = 4.4 \cdot 10^{81} \cdot 1.3 \cdot 10^9 \cdot \frac{10^{-4} \text{ s}}{10^{-29} \text{ s}} \cong 10^{116}$$

The factor β occurs because the annihilation of antibaryons takes place after the rises of light particles.

Considering that the mass of these particles is more than mass of light particles ($n = 12$, $r = 10^{31}$ cm) by a factor 10^{10} , we obtain that its total mass exceeds the mass of substance (baryons) of the Universe. It seems likely that it is hidden mass (invisible halo of galaxies).

By analogy, we may assume that at transition of next level ($n = 10$, weak interaction), e.g. at neutralization of stars and flares of ultra new stars, the rise of large amount of light particle ($n = 10$, $r = 10^{12} \div 10^{13}$ cm) takes also place. This process is favourable to escaping heavy elements and generation of planetary systems.

3. On the association of universal constants with the values α and β

As indicated above, value α is the constant of inflation $e^{144} \cong 3.5 \cdot 10^{62}$. The value β or cosmological value defining the degree of baryon asymmetry of the Universe is equal to the ratio between the amount of relict photons and the amount of baryons:

$$\frac{n_\gamma}{n_B} \cong \frac{400 \frac{1}{\text{cm}^3}}{3 \cdot 10^{-7} \frac{1}{\text{cm}^3}} \cong 1.3 \cdot 10^9 = \beta$$

From the multidimensional geometry it is known that surface of six-dimensional sphere is equal to $S_6 = \frac{16}{15} \pi^3 R^6 \cong 33.07 R^6$, with the dimensionality of space is $n = 7$. The surfaces of five-dimensional sphere and seven-dimensional sphere are accordingly equal to $S_5 = \pi^3 R^5 \cong 31 R^5$, $S_7 = \frac{\pi^4}{3} R^7 \cong 32.47 R^7$. Notice that the surface S_6 has maximum factor 33.07 for all values S_n .

If we suppose that, hand in hand, with inflation, the decay of Planck six-sphere to spheres of radius $33.07 \cdot R$ takes place (that is the rise of substance - χ -protoparticles having mass which is less than Planck mass by factor 33.1), then its amount is equal to:

$$(33.07)^6 \cong 1.3 \cdot 10^9 = \beta.$$

Thus, the $\frac{16}{15} \pi^3$ is equal to $\beta^{1/6}$

The physical values and world constants are measured in centimeter-gramme- second system which is symmetrical to Gaussian system of units wherein, among other factors, $\varepsilon_0 = \mu_0 = 1$. We can assume that the association between these units of measurement of physical values and “large” values α and β is available. The “large” values α and β define as though the scale (range) of its measurements.

If the three scales-time, density and mass – are sketched in all “range” of values from minimum up to maximum values, we obtain

1) $t_{\min} = t_0 = t_{\text{pl}} \cong 5 \cdot 10^{-44}$ s; $t_{\max} = t_0 \cdot \alpha^{4/3} \cdot \beta^{2/6} \cong 2 \cdot 10^{43}$ s, where $t_0 \cdot \alpha^{4/3}$ is life time of nucleons (baryons) ($\sim 10^{40}$ s), and $t_{\max}$ is life time of leptons defined by mass of χ -particle $n = 12$.

$$\bar{t} = 1 \text{ s} = \sqrt{t_{\min} t_{\max}} \approx t_0 \cdot \alpha^{2/3} \cdot \beta^{1/6}$$

$$2) \rho_{\min} = \frac{m_{\text{pl}}}{(\alpha \cdot l_{\text{pl}})^3} = \frac{\rho_{\max}}{\alpha^3} \cong 10^{-94} \text{ g/cm}^3; \rho_{\max} = \rho_{\text{pl}} = \rho_0 \cong 10^{94} \text{ g/cm},$$

$$\bar{\rho} = \sqrt{\rho_{\min} \rho_{\max}} = 1 \text{ g/cm} \approx \frac{m_0}{l_0^3} \cdot \alpha^{-3/2}.$$

3) $m_0 = m_{\text{pl}}$; $m_{\min} = \frac{m_0}{\beta^{1/6} \alpha}$ is mass of lightest particle ($n = 12$); $m_{\max} = m_0 \alpha \beta \beta^{1/6}$ is mass of the

Universe in “hadron era” before annihilation (10^{-4} s);

$$\bar{m} = 1 \text{ g} = \sqrt{m_{\min} m_{\max}} \approx m_0 \beta^{1/2}$$

From 2) and 3) we way obtain that $1 \text{ cm} = \left(\frac{1 \text{ g}}{1 \text{ g/cm}^3} \right)^{1/3}$ and then:

$$\begin{aligned} 1 \text{ cm} &\approx l_0 \cdot \alpha^{1/2} \cdot \beta^{1/6}, \\ 1 \text{ g} &\approx m_0 \cdot \beta^{1/2}, (*) \\ 1 \text{ s} &\approx t_0 \cdot \alpha^{2/3} \cdot \beta^{1/6}. \end{aligned}$$

From these values, we may obtain rough values of the constants:

$$c = \frac{l_0}{t_0} \approx \frac{\alpha^{2/3}}{\alpha^{1/2}} \left(\frac{\text{cm}}{\text{s}} \right) = \alpha^{1/6} \left(\frac{\text{cm}}{\text{s}} \right)$$

- is independent of β .

$$h = \frac{m_0 l_0^2}{t_0} \approx \frac{1g \cdot \beta^{-1/2} \alpha^{-1} \cdot \beta^{-2/6} \text{cm}^2}{1s \cdot \alpha^{-2/3} \cdot \beta^{-1/6}} = \alpha^{-1/3} \cdot \beta^{-2/3} \frac{\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^2}{\text{s}}$$

$$G = \frac{l_0^3}{m_0 t_0^2} \approx \frac{\beta^{1/2} \alpha^{4/3} \cdot \beta^{2/6}}{\alpha^{3/2} \cdot \beta^{3/6}} = \alpha^{-1/6} \cdot \beta^{1/3} \frac{\text{cm}^3}{\text{g} \cdot \text{s}^2}$$

The higher approximation of these constants is arrived multiplying the Eq. (*) in to the constants near 1:

$$\begin{cases} 1\text{cm} = l_0 \cdot \alpha^{1/2} \cdot \beta^{1/6} \cdot k_1, & k_1 = \left(\frac{S_6}{S_7} \right)^{1/6} = 1.0031, \\ 1\text{g} = m_0 \cdot \beta^{1/2} \cdot k_2, & k_2 = \left(\frac{4S_6}{S_5} \right)^{1/6} = 1.2375, \\ 1\text{s} = t_0 \cdot \alpha^{2/3} \cdot \beta^{1/6} \cdot k_3, & k_3 = \left(\frac{2S_6}{S_5} \right)^{1/6} = 1.1346, \end{cases}$$

where S_5, S_6, S_7 – are surfaces of unit spheres in six-, seven- and eight-dimensional space. With these results, we obtain:

$$c = \frac{k_3}{k_1} \alpha^{1/6} = 2.996 \cdot 10^{10} \text{ cm/s},$$

$$h = \frac{k_3}{k_2 k_1^2} \alpha^{-1/3} \cdot \beta^{-2/3} = 1.055 \cdot 10^{-27} (\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^2) / \text{s},$$

$$G = \frac{k_3^2 k_2}{k_1^3} \alpha^{-1/6} \cdot \beta^{1/3} = 6.68 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^3 / (\text{g} \cdot \text{s}^2),$$

where

$$\alpha = e^{144}, \quad \beta^{1/6} = \frac{16}{15} \pi^3$$

4. The alternative description of elementary particles or what is the color of quark

As evident from the Table 1, an electron is particle formed by double motion ($n=0, m_{\text{vir}} = 7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e$) and in its turn $m = 7 \cdot 10^{20} m_e$ at $n = 12$ is “formed” by the motion of particle $m_{\text{vir}} = 2 \cdot 10^{42} m_e$. The radius of single “inside” motion is equal to $\sim 10^{-31}$ cm and the radius of “outside” motion $\sim 10^{-10}$ cm.

The four structure of double motion is available for an electron. Let us schematically depict these structures as:

$$\begin{array}{cccc} e^- & \nu_e & e^+ & \tilde{\nu}_e \\ \uparrow & \uparrow & \downarrow & \downarrow \\ \text{---} & \text{---} & \text{---} & \text{---} \\ \downarrow & \uparrow & \uparrow & \downarrow \\ L = & 1 & 1 & -1 & -1 \end{array}$$

where a bottom arrow indicates the pointing of inside motion from center or to center and a top arrow indicates the pointing of outside motion. Imagine these structures as leptons of zero-level with corresponding values of lepton charge L .

For intermediate bosons $W^\pm$ and Z_0 , ($n = 6$) this structure is:

For component particles e.g. nucleons this structure is

where u and d quarks can be conceived as of

$$\begin{cases} u(0,1,1) \\ d(1,0,1) \end{cases} \quad n_1 \ n_2 \ n_4$$

and value n_0 is responsible of the “color” of quark. Quark d has color $\tilde{\nu}_e, e^+, e^-$ and quark u^- has color $\tilde{\nu}_e, e^+, \nu_e$.

For the nucleons and antinucleons, the four combinations from four values by three values are may be made. Color of e^- and ν_e has identical lepton number $L = 1$ but different charge stations.

The decay takes play by scheme: $n_0 \rightarrow p^+ + W^- \rightarrow p^+ + e^- + \tilde{\nu}_e$

- 1) $e^- \rightarrow W^- + \nu_e$.
- 2) $W^- \rightarrow e^- + \tilde{\nu}$

(The decay of d - quark of color « e^- » in to u -quark of color « ν_e » and W^- - boson that is $d \rightarrow u + W^-$).

The masses of proton and neutron can be expressed as

$$m_p = [\bar{L}(\bar{L} + L) \cdot n_1 \cdot 1,4 + L(\bar{L} + L)(\bar{L} - L) \cdot n_2 \cdot 3,8] \cdot 207m_e,$$

$$m_n = [L(\bar{L} + L) \cdot n_1 \cdot 1.4 + \bar{L}(\bar{L} + L)(\bar{L} - L) \cdot n_2 \cdot 3.8] \cdot 207m_e,$$

where $\bar{L} = 2$ and $L = 1$ for nucleon, $n_1 = 1, n_2 = 2$ for proton and $n_1 = 2, n_2 = 1$ for neutron.

Thus, we obtain that

$$m_p = [\bar{L} \cdot 3 \cdot n_1 \cdot 1.4 + L \cdot 3 \cdot n_2 \cdot 3.8] \cdot 207 = 6(1.4 + 3.8)207 = 31.2 \cdot 207,$$

$$m_n = [L \cdot 3 \cdot n_1 \cdot 1.4 + \bar{L} \cdot 3 \cdot n_2 \cdot 3.8] \cdot 207 = 6(1.4 + 3.8)207 = 31.2 \cdot 207,$$

that is more than three times larger than mass of nucleon. Hence, more than 2/3 of this energy is bond energy of quarks in nucleon. Thus the mass of nucleon is equal to 1/3 of this energy minus the bond energy of single pion (~ 150 MeV).

For the π - mesons the structure is:

The mass of π^+ and π^- meson is:

$$m_{\pi^+} = m_{\pi^-} = (1 \cdot 2 \cdot n_1 \cdot 1.4 + 0 \cdot 3 \cdot n_2 \cdot 3.8) \cdot 207m_e,$$

that is two times larger than mass of meson. Thus, 1/2 of this energy is the bond energy of quarks in meson.

The difference of $|\bar{L} - L|$ may be equal to 1, for nucleon or 0 for meson.

The decay of pion takes place by scheme:

$$\pi^- \rightarrow \mu^- + \tilde{\nu}_\mu, \mu^-(\bar{u}), \tilde{\nu}_\mu(d) \text{ see below.}$$

The muon and muon neutrino have the following quarkless "structure" :

The decay of muon takes place by scheme:

The electron neutrino gains the rest mass and escapes a particle at the instant of transitions $n_2 \leftrightarrow n_1$ (see scheme for nucleons). The evaluation of rest mass for neutrino as the variation of gravitational energy of virtual

particle $m_{vir} = 1.3 \cdot 10^{19} m_e$ ($n = 2$) in the gravitational field of electron $\frac{Gm_e m_{vir(n=2)}}{r_2} \cong m_{0\nu_e}$, where $r_2 \sim$

$2.5 \cdot 10^{-31}$ cm, will be in the region of 1.8 eV, for $m_{0\nu_e}$.

Not counting corrections introducing by $m_{vir,4,5}$ ($n = 4,5$), that is

$$\frac{m_{0\nu_\mu} - m_{0\nu_e}}{m_{0\nu_e}} \sim 10^{-8}, \quad \frac{m_{0\nu_\tau} - m_{0\nu_e}}{m_{0\nu_e}} \sim 10^{-12},$$

the rest mass ν_μ and ν_τ is close equal to $m_{0\nu_e}$.

5. The cosmological constant (the density of vacuum) and the relationship between the cosmic energies

1. Recent astronomical research has shown that the density of vacuum is

$$\rho_V \cong 2 \cdot 10^{-123} \rho_{pl},$$

where ρ_{pl} is Planck density.

From the preceding, the density of baryon substance is would be expressible as:

$$\rho_B = \frac{M_U}{V_U} = \frac{\alpha \cdot m_{pl}}{\left(\alpha \cdot \frac{l_{pl}}{2}\right)^3} = \frac{8}{\alpha^2 \cdot \rho_{pl}},$$

where $\alpha = e^{144} \cong 3.5 \cdot 10^{62}$ that is $\rho_B = \frac{8}{10^{125}} \rho_{pl}$ and it is smaller than the above- mentioned density of vacuum by a factor of 25.

However, notice that the ρ_V is variable value. It is invariable up to $\sim 10^{31}$ cm and then it will fall as $\frac{1}{R^3}$.

2. According to this recent astronomical research, the ratio of density of vacuum to critical density, that is its contribution to the total mass, is

$$\Omega_V = \frac{\rho_V}{\rho_c} = 0.7 \pm 0.1,$$

the contribution of dark substance of galaxies is

$$\Omega_D = \frac{\rho_D}{\rho_c} = 0,3 \pm 0,1$$

and contribution of baryons is

$$\Omega_B = \frac{\rho_B}{\rho_c} = 0.03 \pm 0.01$$

Then, the contribution of fourth component of cosmic medium that is radiation or ultra relativistic medium is equal to

$$\Omega_R = \frac{\rho_R}{\rho_c} = 0.8 \cdot 10^{-5} k, 1 < k < 10 \div 30.$$

These ratios may be explained in terms of the above mentioned hypothesis.

3. Let us turn back to Table 1. Suppose that, at $n = 12$, the particles with radius $\sim 10^{31}$ cm produce a repulsion field (space curvature is negative). This is the so-called vacuum. At $n = 11$, the particles with radius $\sim 10^{21}$ cm produce an attraction field (space curvature is positive). This is the so-called dark substance of galaxies.

At $n = 10$, the particles with radius $\sim 10^{13}$ cm produce a repulsion field too (space curvature is negative). These fields are responsible for the origination of planetary systems (the before planet cloud).

At $n < 10$, this alternation is being continued. It is conceivable that these particles (fields) are responsible for the formation of protoplanetary bodies with the asteroid dimensions from the before planet cloud (at $n = 9$), for the nanoeffects (Kazimir's forces) (at $n = 8$) and for the synthesis of heavy elements (at $n = 7$).

Let us make round estimates of amount and total mass of these particles ($n = 12, 11, 10$) which are originated at the instant the "Big Bang" takes place:

$$N_{12} \sim \frac{T_{12}}{\tau_{12}} \cdot \beta \cdot N$$

where T_{12} is time t_0 until the completion of this stage (era);

$$T_{12} \sim 10^{-6} \text{ s}, \tau_{12} \sim 33.1 \cdot \tau_{p1} = 1.7 \cdot 10^{-42} \text{ s},$$

τ_{12} – characteristic time of process (the birth of particles),

$\beta = 1.3 \cdot 10^9$ is factor of baryon asymmetry since the process takes place before the annihilation of baryons,

$N = 4.4 \cdot 10^{81}$ is amount of baryons (quarks) in processes quark $\leftrightarrow$ lepton,

$$N_{12} \sim \frac{10^{-6} \text{ s}}{1.7 \cdot 10^{-42} \text{ s}} \cdot 1.3 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 4.4 \cdot 10^{81} \cong 3 \cdot 10^{126}$$

In similar manner, at $n = 11$ (the transitions quark $\leftrightarrow$ baryon, hadron era)

$$N_{11} \sim \frac{1.5 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}}{1.7 \cdot 10^{-29} \text{ s}} \cdot 1.3 \cdot 10^9 \cdot 4.4 \cdot 10^{81} \cong 10^{116}$$

At $n = 10$ (transitions $n \leftrightarrow p$, lepton era)

$$N_{10} \sim \frac{1 \text{ s}}{10^{-20} \text{ s}} \cdot 4.4 \cdot 10^{81} \cong 4 \cdot 10^{101}$$

where $10^{-20} \text{ s} = \tau_{ew}$ is time of electroweak processes and when the factor β is eliminated.

The ratio between masses of these particles is

$$\frac{m_{12}}{m_{11}} \sim \frac{2 \cdot 10^{-42} m_e}{2 \cdot 10^{-32} m_e} = 10^{-10}, \frac{m_{11}}{m_{10}} \sim \frac{2 \cdot 10^{-32} m_e}{2.6 \cdot 10^{-23} m_e} = 10^{-9}$$

and then the ratio between the total contributions is

$$\frac{M_{12}}{M_{11}} \sim 2 \div 4, \frac{M_{10}}{M_{11}} \sim 2 \cdot 10^{-5}, M = m \cdot N.$$

1. Let us turn back to a consideration of baryons. Baryon is not simple fivedimensional sphere of size $\sim 10^{31}$ cm. It is particle of substance having the fields of strong, Coulomb and weak interactions. For fivedimensional sphere (the space inside is sixdimensional and has 3+1+ mass + spin) the surface area is

$$\pi^3 R^5 = S_5 = 31.006 R^5$$

that is the compactification or reduction factor is equal to 31. The vacuum surrounding baryons is fivedimensional (3+1+ mass or curvature).

Thus, it is felt that after the decay substance the space curvature will be fully compensated as initially the total curvature is equal to zero. That is at decay (i.e. reducing the baryon dimensionality by 1) the baryons are to

be annihilated with space. The mass of these baryons are $\frac{1}{31}$ part (or 3.2%) of total mass of the Universe. The disturbance of bilateral symmetry in the decay of matter particles is a manifestation of this effect. To ensure the

compensation of general curvature the attraction and repulsion fields in baryons are to be in energetic and integral balance with the corresponding fields of the Universe.

The Universe is electrically neutral i.e. electric charge is fully compensated. The baryon charge is not compensated.

Let us turn back to Table 1. Suppose that the quark $\begin{pmatrix} d \\ 1.4 \end{pmatrix}$ creates the attraction field at $n = 1$ and the quark $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ 3.8 \end{pmatrix}$ creates the repulsion field at $n = 2$. At $n = 3$ quark $\begin{pmatrix} c \\ 20 \end{pmatrix}$ creates the attraction field too. Thus, the u and d quarks are liable to form combination wherein the size of attraction area $\left(\sim \frac{1}{m_d} \sim 1.9 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ cm} \right)$ stands out

above the size of repulsion area $\left(\sim \frac{1}{m_u} \sim 0.7 \cdot 10^{-13} \text{ cm} \right)$ and the repulsive potential i.e. core is large than attractive potential by a factor $\frac{W(-)}{W(+)} = \frac{3.8}{1.4} = e$.

As total curvature of the Universe is equal to zero and space (space energies) is “antimatter” for baryons, the given below ratio may be written:

$$\frac{\rho_V}{\rho_D} = \frac{W(-)}{W(+)} = e$$

The constant of weak interaction is five orders less than the constant of strong interaction, this is in accordance with the ratio:

$$\frac{\rho_R}{\rho_V} \ll 1$$

Thus, doing not take into account the contribution of ρ_R , it may be roughly written as:

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_V + \Omega_D + \Omega_B \cong 1, \\ \frac{\Omega_V}{\Omega_D} = e, \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_R \ll 1, \quad \Omega_B = \frac{1}{\pi^3} \cong \frac{1}{31}$$

We can apply this relationships to give

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_V = \frac{e \left(1 - \frac{1}{\pi^3} \right)}{1 + e} = 0.7075 \cong 70.8\%, \\ \Omega_D \cong 0.26 = 26\%, \\ \Omega_B \cong 3.2\%, \end{cases}$$

this is in good agreement with the last experimental data.

Conclusion

An effort is made to associate the relationships controlling the world of elementary particles and the Universe as a whole. The standard model of elementary particles adequately describes observations. However, this model postulates the values of particle masses and does not use the concepts explaining relationship among these masses. Hence, it is significantly describing theory and its development is previously advanced by experimental results. It is suggested that this model will be faced problems of explanation of facts which will be occurred in the course of the energy increasing of colliders. There are failed detections of Higgs' bosons and new particles in range about 6 TeV.

It is also unlikely that progress in search for exotic massive particles forming the dark matter in surrounding space will be made as this matter is surrounding space with some energy density.

This work is not of course fundamental theory for all properties of elementary particles and the Universe. The hypothesis supporting the body of known facts is only reported. It is conceivable that a some integration of the standard model of elementary particles with modern cosmology and hypothesis outlined above will furnish insights into the nature of problem.